

Stability of Higher Dimensional Plane Symmetric Space-Time with Wet Dark Fluid Within the Framework of $f(R, T)$ Theory of Gravity.

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Abstract

In this research article, we focus on the investigation of the stability of five-dimensional Plane symmetric space-time with Wet Dark Fluid in the presence of $f(R, T)$ theory of gravitation. We use Hubble's law to find the exact solution. Also, we studied the physical parameters of the model in terms of redshift and explained the energy conditions, stability of the model, and statefinder parameter of the model. We also discussed look-back time, proper distance, luminosity distance, angular diameter, cosmic snap parameter, and jerk parameter and their graphical representation.

Keywords: Deceleration parameter, $f(R, T)$ theory of gravitation, Five-dimensional plane symmetric space-time, Wet dark fluid.

1. Introduction

General Relativity is a mathematically and observationally successful theory of gravitation. The motion and evolution of large-scale cosmic structures such as galaxies, galaxy clusters, stars, and planetary systems are fundamentally governed by gravity. This concept is central to understanding the curvature and deformation of space-time. The reformulation of gravity in terms of space-time curvature, as introduced by Einstein's General Relativity (GR), has revolutionized our comprehension of the universe. GR faces limitations in explaining the full nature of Dark Energy and Dark Matter. Consequently, modifications to GR have been extensively pursued. These modifications generally follow two approaches i.e. (1) altering the Einstein field equations directly and (2) extending the geometric framework of GR via modified gravity theories, such as

scalar-tensor theories, which modify the left-hand side of the field equations. Among the various modified theories such as $f(R)$ gravity, $f(T)$ gravity, $f(G)$ gravity, and $f(R, T)$ gravity have emerged as compelling alternatives. These theories adjust the geometric sector of GR to explain the observed cosmic acceleration without requiring exotic dark energy. In particular, $f(R, T)$ gravity in which the gravitational Lagrangian is a general function of the Ricci scalar and the trace of the energy-momentum tensor has gained significant attention. $f(R, T)$ theory introduces a matter-geometry coupling that can produce additional gravitational effects, potentially accounting for late-time acceleration. It also provides a framework for unifying early-time inflation with the current acceleration phase. Notable contributions in this area include works by (Shamir, 2015), (Mete & Mule, 2017), (Shaikh & Wankhade, 2017), (Chundawat & Mehta, 2021), (Pradhan, et al., 2023), (Thakare, et al., 2023) studied $f(R, T)$ theory of gravity.

In addition to modifications of gravity, higher-dimensional cosmological models have been extensively investigated as tools for understanding the early universe. Inspired by advances in unification theories such as string theory, M-theory, and supergravity, the idea that our 4-Dimensional universe may be a lower-dimensional hypersurface embedded in a higher-dimensional manifold has become a cornerstone of modern theoretical physics. Higher-dimensional frameworks provide geometric unification of all interactions, and offer alternative explanations for dark energy, dark matter, inflation, and cosmic anisotropies. Such models also provide insight into processes like dimensional compactification and isotropization during the early stages of cosmic evolution. Several authors have made significant contributions to this area of research including (Xu & Lu, 2005), (Aguilar & Romero, 2009), (Reddy & Naidu, 2009), (Samanta, et al., 2014), (Sahoo, 2017), (Pawar, et al., 2023), (Thakre, et al., 2024), (Daimary & Baruah, 2024), (Oli & Santhosh, 2025).

Cosmology reveals that the universe is primarily composed of two enigmatic components i.e. dark energy (DE) and dark matter (DM), both playing crucial roles in the cosmic expansion process. Dark energy, characterized by its negative pressure, is believed to drive the observed accelerated expansion of the universe. Although it exerts a repulsive gravitational effect, its fundamental nature remains largely unknown. Within the framework of GR, DE is typically modeled as an isotropic fluid with constant energy density and negative pressure. Among the proposed candidates for DE, the cosmological constant (Λ) stands out due to its simplicity and consistency with observational data. However, uncertainties surrounding the true origin of cosmic acceleration have prompted a surge of interest in exploring alternatives to GR. Significant observational evidence for accelerated expansion comes from high-redshift Type Ia supernovae, particularly through the efforts of the High- z Supernova Search Team. These observations suggest that the best-fitting cosmological model includes a nonzero cosmological constant and a negative deceleration parameter. Additional support for this conclusion arises from studies of cosmic microwave background radiation (CMBR) anisotropies, baryon acoustic oscillations (BAO), large-scale structure surveys, and weak gravitational lensing. These datasets collectively support a nearly flat spatial geometry for the present universe. To better explain the late-time acceleration,

numerous dynamical dark energy models have been proposed, characterized by an evolving equation of state (EoS) parameter. While the Λ CDM model remains the most prominent, several scalar field-based models, such as quintessence, phantom, k-essence, tachyon, and quintom fields, have been actively studied. Additionally, interacting dark energy models, such as the Chaplygin gas and holographic dark energy, offer alternative approaches. A notable candidate among these models is the Wet Dark Fluid (WDF), introduced by (Holman & Naidu, 2004). Inspired by the generalized Chaplygin gas model (Gorini, et al., 2005). WDF arises from an empirical equation of state originally developed to describe the properties of water and aqueous solutions (Hayward, 1967); (Tait, 1988). The equation of state for WDF is given by,

$$p_{WDF} = \gamma(\rho_{WDF} - \rho^*), \quad (1)$$

here p_{WDF} is the pressure of WDF and ρ_{WDF} represents the energy density of WDF. In this equation, the parameters ρ^* and γ are taken to be positive, and we restrict our analysis to the range $0 < \gamma < 1$. This formulation, based on the behavior of real fluids, allows for negative pressure due to intermolecular forces. Here $\gamma = c_s^2$ given by (Babichev, et al., 2004) and c_s denotes the adiabatic sound speed in wet dark fluid. In the literature, many researchers (Adhav, et al., 2011), (Ravishankar, et al., 2013), (Sarkar, 2015), (Chirde & Shekh, 2016), (Mahanta, 2017), (Samanta & Bishi, 2017), (Angit, et al., 2019), (Singh, et al., 2021), (Shobhane & Deo, 2021), (Pawar, et al., 2024) studied a wet dark fluid cosmological model.

In the present study, to provide deeper insights into the universe's accelerated expansion and the role of higher dimensions in shaping cosmic evolution, we investigate the cosmological dynamics of a higher-dimensional plane symmetric cosmological model within the framework of $f(R, T)$ gravity, incorporating the Wet Dark Fluid model as a candidate for dark energy. This paper contains nine sections, with brief information about $f(R, T)$ theory of gravity presented in section 2. Section 3 contains metric and field equations, Section 4 includes solutions of five-dimensional plane symmetric space-time and kinematical parameters of the model. In section 5, we have studied the stability of the model, section 6 described the energy condition of the model, and in section 7, we described the statefinder parameter. Discussion and observational constraints are contained in section 8, and finally, in section 9, the conclusion of the study.

2. $f(R, T)$ Theory of Gravity

The field equation for $f(R, T)$ theory of gravity is derived from the action

$$S = \frac{1}{16\pi} \int [f(R, T) + L_m] \sqrt{-g} d^4x \quad (2)$$

Where $f(R, T)$ is an arbitrary function of Ricci scalar R and trace T of energy momentum tensor T_{ij} and L_m is the matter Lagrangian.

The energy-momentum tensor T_{ij} is defined as

$$T_{ij} = -\frac{2\delta(\sqrt{-g}L_m)}{\sqrt{-g}\delta g_{ij}} \quad (3)$$

Here, we consider that the dependence of the matter Lagrangian is merely on g_{ij} i.e., metric tensor rather than on its derivatives.

$$T_{ij} = L_m g_{ij} - 2\frac{\delta L_m}{\delta g^{ij}} \quad (4)$$

Now, by varying the action S in equation (2.1) with respect to the metric tensor g_{ij} the field equations of $f(R, T)$ gravity is obtained as

$$f_R(R, T)R_{ij} - \frac{1}{2}f(R, T)g_{ij} - (\nabla_i \nabla_j - g_{ij}\square)f_R(R, T) = 8\pi T_{ij} - f_T(R, T)(T_{ij} + \theta_{ij}) \quad (5)$$

Where ∇_i denotes the covariant derivative and $\square = \nabla^i \nabla_j$, $\theta_{ij} = g^{lk} \frac{\delta T_{lk}}{\delta g^{ij}}$.

Now contracting eq. (2.4) We obtained

$$f_R(R, T)R + 3\square f_R(R, T) - 2f(R, T) = 8\pi T - f_T(R, T)(T + \theta) \quad (6)$$

Where $\theta = \theta_i^i$. This equation is important because it gives a relation between the Ricci scalar and the trace T of the energy-momentum tensor.

In this paper, we assume the energy-momentum tensor for a wet dark fluid T_{ij} is

$$T_{ij} = (p_{WDF} + \rho_{WDF})u_i u_j + p_{WDF}g_{ij} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{With } g_{ij}u^i u^j = 1 \quad (8)$$

where p_{WDF} is the pressure of the wet dark fluid, ρ_{WDF} is the density of wet dark fluid and u_i is the five velocity vector of the fluid. Here, we assume the matter Lagrangian as $L_m = -p$ which gives

$$\theta_{ij} = -p g_{ij} - 2T_{ij} \quad (9)$$

And then the field equation takes the form

$$f_R(R, T)R_{ij} - \frac{1}{2}f(R, T)g_{ij} - (\nabla_i \nabla_j - g_{ij}\square)f_R(R, T) = 8\pi T_{ij} f_T(R, T)(T_{ij} + p g_{ij}) \quad (10)$$

Many theoretical models are possible, corresponding to different matter contributions for $f(R, T)$ gravity. However, (Harko, et al., 2011) gave three different classes of these models:

$$f(R, T) = \begin{cases} R + 2f(T) \\ f_1(R) + f_2(T) \\ f_1(R) + f_2(R)f_3(T) \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

In this article, we studied the case $f(R, T) = R + 2f(T)$. In this particular case, the form of the field equation is

$$R_{ij} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{ij} = 8\pi T_{ij} + 2f'(T)T_{ij} + [f(T) + 2pf'(T)]g_{ij} \quad (12)$$

Here we choose $f(T) = \lambda T$.

3. Metric and field equations

The five-dimensional plane symmetric space-time is

$$ds^2 = dt^2 - A_1^2(dx^2 + dy^2) - A_2^2 dz^2 - A_3^2 du^2 \quad (13)$$

Where A_1, A_2, A_3 are the functions of cosmic time t only.

From (7), (8), and (13), equation (12) becomes

$$\frac{\ddot{A}_1}{A_1} + \frac{\ddot{A}_2}{A_2} + \frac{\ddot{A}_3}{A_3} + \frac{\dot{A}_1 \dot{A}_2}{A_1 A_2} + \frac{\dot{A}_1 \dot{A}_3}{A_1 A_3} + \frac{\dot{A}_2 \dot{A}_3}{A_2 A_3} = -8\pi p_{WDF} - 10\lambda p_{WDF} - \lambda \rho_{WDF} \quad (14)$$

$$2\frac{\ddot{A}_1}{A_1} + \frac{\ddot{A}_3}{A_3} + 2\frac{\dot{A}_1 \dot{A}_3}{A_1 A_3} + \left(\frac{\dot{A}_1}{A_1}\right)^2 = -8\pi p_{WDF} - 10\lambda p_{WDF} - \lambda \rho_{WDF} \quad (15)$$

$$2\frac{\ddot{A}_1}{A_1} + \frac{\ddot{A}_2}{A_2} + 2\frac{\dot{A}_1 \dot{A}_2}{A_1 A_2} + \left(\frac{\dot{A}_1}{A_1}\right)^2 = 8\pi p_{WDF} - 10\lambda p_{WDF} - \lambda \rho_{WDF} \quad (16)$$

$$2\frac{\dot{A}_1 \dot{A}_2}{A_1 A_2} + 2\frac{\dot{A}_1 \dot{A}_3}{A_1 A_3} + \frac{\dot{A}_2 \dot{A}_3}{A_2 A_3} + \left(\frac{\dot{A}_1}{A_1}\right)^2 = -(16\pi + 12\lambda)p_{WDF} - (8\pi + 3\lambda)\rho_{WDF} \quad (17)$$

Here, the overhead dot on the A_1, A_2, A_3 denotes ordinary differentiation with respect to time t .

The kinematical parameter is defined as follows:

$$\text{The average scale factor } R \text{ is defined as } R = (A_1^2 A_2 A_3)^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad (18)$$

$$\text{The volume } V \text{ is defined as } V = R^4(t) = A_1^2 A_2 A_3 \quad (19)$$

$$\text{The Hubble parameter } H \text{ is defined as } H = \frac{1}{4} (H_x + H_y + H_z + H_u) \quad (20)$$

Where H_x, H_y, H_z, H_u are the directional Hubble's parameters along X, Y, Z, U axis respectively.

$$H_x = \frac{\dot{P}_1}{P_1}, H_y = \frac{\dot{P}_2}{P_2}, H_z = \frac{\dot{P}_3}{P_3}, H_u = \frac{\dot{P}_4}{P_4} \quad (21)$$

The Average anisotropic expansion parameter A_m , shear scalar σ^2 and expansion scalar θ is given by

$$A_m = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{i=1}^4 \left(\frac{\Delta H_i}{H}\right)^2, \quad \Delta H_i = H_i - H \quad (22)$$

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1}{2} (\sum_{i=1}^4 H_i^2 - 4H^2) = \frac{1}{2} (H_x^2 + H_y^2 + H_z^2 + H_u^2 - \frac{\theta^2}{4}) \quad (23)$$

$$\theta = 2\frac{\dot{A}_1}{A_1} + \frac{\dot{A}_2}{A_2} + \frac{\dot{A}_3}{A_3} \quad (24)$$

$$\text{The deceleration parameter } q \text{ is defined as } q = \frac{-\ddot{R}R}{\dot{R}^2} \quad (25)$$

4. Solution of field equations and kinematical parameters of the model

From field equation (14)-(17), we get,

$$\frac{A_1}{A_2} = a_1 \exp\left(b_1 \int \frac{dt}{V}\right) \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{A_2}{A_3} = a_2 \exp\left(b_2 \int \frac{dt}{V}\right) \quad (27)$$

$$\frac{A_1}{A_3} = a_3 \exp\left(b_3 \int \frac{dt}{V}\right) \quad (28)$$

Where a_1, a_2, a_3 and b_1, b_2, b_3 are integrating constants that satisfy the relation $a_3 = a_2 a_1$ and $b_3 = b_2 + b_1$.

From equation (26)-(28), the metric function A_1, A_2 and A_3 can be written as

$$A_1(t) = C_1 V^{\frac{1}{4}} \exp\left(D_1 \int \frac{dt}{V}\right) \quad (29)$$

$$A_2(t) = C_2 V^{\frac{1}{4}} \exp\left(D_2 \int \frac{dt}{V}\right) \quad (30)$$

$$A_3(t) = C_3 V^{\frac{1}{4}} \exp\left(D_3 \int \frac{dt}{V}\right) \quad (31)$$

Where integrating constants C_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) and D_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) satisfying $C_1^2 C_2 C_3 = 1$ and $2D_1 + D_2 + D_3 = 0$.

The field equations (14)-(17) are differential equations with five unknowns $A_1, A_2, A_3, p_{WDF}, \rho_{WDF}$. To find the complete solution of the above field equations, we require one physical condition. Hence, we use the relation between the Hubble parameter H and average scale factor R which is proposed by (Berman, 1983) and (Berman & de Mello Gomide, 1988) which is given by

$$H = \frac{B}{R^n}, \quad B > 0 \text{ and } n \geq 0 \text{ both are constant.} \quad (32)$$

From equations (25) and (32), we get

$$q = n - 1 \quad (33)$$

On solving equations (32) and (33), we obtained the law of the average scale factor R as the form

$$R = (nBt)^{\frac{1}{n}} \text{ for } n \neq 0. \quad (34)$$

$$\text{Hence the volume } V = (nBt)^{\frac{4}{n}} \text{ for } n \neq 0. \quad (35)$$

Using (35) in equations (29)-(31), we get

$$A_1(t) = C_1(nBt)^{\frac{1}{n}} \exp \left[\frac{D_1}{(n-4)B} (nBt)^{\frac{n-4}{n}} \right], \quad n \neq 4 \quad (36)$$

$$A_2(t) = C_2(nBt)^{\frac{1}{n}} \exp \left[\frac{D_2}{(n-4)B} (nBt)^{\frac{n-4}{n}} \right], \quad n \neq 4 \quad (37)$$

$$A_3(t) = C_3(nBt)^{\frac{1}{n}} \exp \left[\frac{D_3}{(n-4)B} (nBt)^{\frac{n-4}{n}} \right], \quad n \neq 4 \quad (38)$$

where, $C_1^2 C_2 C_3 = 1$ and $2D_1 + D_2 + D_3 = 0$.

Then, from equations (36)-(38), the five-dimensional plane symmetric space-time with wet dark fluid becomes

$$ds^2 = dt^2 - \left\{ C_1(nBt)^{\frac{1}{n}} \exp \left[\frac{D_1}{(n-4)B} (nBt)^{\frac{n-4}{n}} \right] \right\}^2 (dx^2 + dy^2) - \left\{ C_2(nBt)^{\frac{1}{n}} \exp \left[\frac{D_2}{(n-4)B} (nBt)^{\frac{n-4}{n}} \right] \right\}^2 dz^2 - \left\{ C_3(nBt)^{\frac{1}{n}} \exp \left[\frac{D_3}{(n-4)B} (nBt)^{\frac{n-4}{n}} \right] \right\}^2 du^2 \quad (39)$$

$$\text{The mean Hubble parameter } H \text{ is obtained as } H = \frac{1}{nt} \quad (40)$$

The shear scalar σ^2 and expansion scalar θ is obtained as

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{D(nBt)^{-\frac{8}{n}}}{2}, \quad \text{where } D = 2D_1^2 + D_2^2 + D_3^2 \quad (41)$$

$$\theta = \frac{4}{nt} \quad (42)$$

The Average anisotropic expansion parameter A_m is obtained as

$$A_m = \frac{D(nBt)^{-\frac{8}{n}+2}}{4B^2}, \quad D = 2D_1^2 + D_2^2 + D_3^2 \quad (43)$$

Energy density ρ_{WDF} of the WDF model is

$$\rho_{WDF} = \frac{1}{(8\pi+\lambda-8\lambda\gamma)} \left[M(nBt)^{-\frac{8}{n}} + 6(nt)^{-2} + 8\lambda\gamma\rho^* \right] \quad (44)$$

Pressure p_{WDF} of WDF model is

$$p_{WDF} = \frac{\gamma}{(8\pi + \lambda - 8\lambda\gamma)} \left[M(nBt)^{-\frac{8}{n}} + 6(nt)^{-2} + 8\lambda\gamma\rho^* \right] - \gamma\rho^* \quad (45)$$

where $M = 3D_1 + 2D_3 + D_2 - D_1D_2 + D_1D_3$.

By using $1 + z = \frac{R_0}{R}$ where R is the scale factor (Piattella, 2018), the above kinetic parameters in terms of redshift z are as follows:

The mean Hubble parameter H in terms of redshift is

$$H = B(1 + z)^n. \quad (46)$$

The shear scalar σ^2 and expansion scalar θ in terms of redshift z are

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{D(1+z)^8}{2}, \quad D = 2D_1^2 + D_2^2 + D_3^2. \quad (47)$$

$$\theta = 4B(1 + z)^n. \quad (48)$$

The Average anisotropic expansion parameter A_m in terms of redshift is

$$A_m = \frac{D(nB)^{-\frac{8}{n}+2}(1+z)^{8-2n}}{4B^2}. \quad (49)$$

Fig. 1

Fig.2

By choosing an appropriate constant, Fig.1 and Fig. 2 indicate variations of the Hubble parameter (H) and expansion scalar (θ) against redshift (z) respectively.

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

By choosing an appropriate constant, Fig.3 and Fig. 4 indicate variations of the shear scalar (σ^2) and anisotropic parameter (Δ) against redshift (z) in respectively.

The energy density of wet dark fluid in terms of redshift z is

$$\rho_{WDF} = \frac{1}{(8\pi + \lambda - 8\lambda\gamma)} [M(1+z)^8 + 6B^2(1+z)^{2n} + 8\lambda\gamma\rho^*] \tag{50}$$

The pressure of wet dark fluid in terms of redshift z is

$$p_{WDF} = \frac{\gamma}{(8\pi + \lambda - 8\lambda\gamma)} [M(1+z)^8 + 6B^2(1+z)^{2n} + 8\lambda\gamma\rho^*] - \gamma\rho^* \tag{51}$$

Fig.5

Fig.6

By choosing an appropriate constant, Fig.5 and Fig. 6 indicates variation of WDF energy density (ρ_{WDF}) against redshift (z) in 2D and 3D respectively.

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

Fig.7 and Fig. 8 indicate the variation of WDF pressure (p_{WDF}) against redshift (z) in 2D and 3D respectively.

5. Stability of the model

The stability of the model is examined through the analysis of the ratio of sound speed given by $\frac{dp}{d\rho} = C_s^2$. The model is considered stable when $C_s^2 > 0$, i. e. $\frac{dp}{d\rho} > 0$, indicates that the pressure increases with energy density. Also, the model becomes unstable when $C_s^2 < 0$, i. e. $\frac{dp}{d\rho} < 0$, which indicates a negative response of pressure to a change in energy density, investigated by (Shaikh, et al., 2021).

For the present model, we calculate $\frac{dp_{WDF}}{d\rho_{WDF}} = \gamma$

Here we choose a range of the parameter γ is $0 < \gamma < 1$ thus, it is clear that the model is stable for the range $0 < \gamma < 1$.

6. Energy Conditions of the Model

The energy conditions play an important role in understanding the physical conditions and gravitational behavior of cosmological models. For the considered model, we discussed the standard energy conditions: the Weak Energy Condition (WEC), Null Energy Condition (NEC), Dominant Energy Condition (DEC), and Strong Energy Condition (SEC).

(i) Weak Energy Condition (WEC)

The WEC satisfies if $\rho_{WDF} \geq 0, \rho_{WDF} + p_{WDF} \geq 0$ i. e. $\rho_{WDF} \geq \frac{\gamma}{(1+\gamma)} \rho^*$.

For the considered model, WEC is satisfied if

$$\frac{1}{(8\pi+\lambda-8\lambda\gamma)} [M(1+z)^8 + 6B^2(1+z)^{2n} + 8\lambda\gamma\rho^*] \geq 0 \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{1}{(8\pi+\lambda-8\lambda\gamma)} [M(1+z)^8 + 6B^2(1+z)^{2n} + 8\lambda\gamma\rho^*] \geq \frac{\gamma}{(1+\gamma)}\rho^*.$$

(ii) Null Energy Condition (NEC)

The NEC satisfies if $\rho_{WDF} + p_{WDF} \geq 0$.

Which is identical to the second condition of the WEC.

(iii) Dominant Energy Condition (DEC)

The DEC satisfies if $\rho_{WDF} \geq 0, \rho_{WDF} - |p_{WDF}| \geq 0$.

This condition gives two possibilities,

- a) $\rho_{WDF} \geq p_{WDF} = \gamma(\rho_{WDF} - \rho^*)$ if $\rho_{WDF} \geq \rho^*$.
- b) $\rho_{WDF} \geq p_{WDF} = \gamma(\rho_{WDF} - \rho^*)$ if $\rho_{WDF} < \rho^*$.

For both cases $\rho_{WDF} \geq \frac{\gamma}{(1+\gamma)}\rho^*$.

For our model,

$$\frac{1}{(8\pi+\lambda-8\lambda\gamma)} [M(1+z)^8 + 6B^2(1+z)^{2n} + 8\lambda\gamma\rho^*] \geq \frac{\gamma}{(1+\gamma)}\rho^*.$$

This also coincides with the weak energy condition.

(iv) Strong Energy Condition (SEC)

The SEC is satisfied if $\rho_{WDF} + 3p_{WDF} \geq 0$.

For the considered model, the SEC is satisfied if

$$\frac{1}{(8\pi+\lambda-8\lambda\gamma)} [M(1+z)^8 + 6B^2(1+z)^{2n} + 8\lambda\gamma\rho^*] \geq \frac{3\gamma}{(1+3\gamma)}\rho^*.$$

Therefore, the WEC, NEC, DEC, and SEC are all satisfied, which means the WDF model can not explain an accelerated expansion of the universe. The WDF model depicts a stable, non-exotic cosmological fluid.

Fig. 9

Fig. 10

Fig. 9 and Fig.10 indicates the graphical representation of WEC and SEC respectively with respect to redshift z .

7. The statefinder parameter

The statefinder parameters $\{r, s\}$ is the new pair of parameters proposed by (Sahni, et al., 2003) and (Alam, et al., 2003). By using statefinder parameters we can examine the expansion history of the universe through higher derivatives of the expansion factor. Different values of statefinder parameter pair $\{r, s\}$ exhibit different dark energy model, i.e. for Quintessence model, $r < 1, s > 0$, for Λ CDM model, $r = 1, s = 0$, for SCDM model, $r = 1, s = 1$, for HDE model, $r = 1, s = \frac{2}{3}$, for CG model $r > 1, s < 0$.The statefinder pair is defined as

$$r = q + 2q^2 - \frac{\dot{q}}{H} = \frac{\ddot{R}}{RH^3} \quad \text{and} \quad s = \frac{r-1}{3(q-\frac{1}{2})}$$

For our model (4.14), the statefinder parameters pair $\{r, s\}$ is obtained as

$$r = 2n^2 - 3n + 1 \quad \text{and} \quad s = \frac{2(2n^2-3n+1)}{3(2n-3)} \tag{52}$$

The relation between the statefinder parameter r and s is $r = \frac{9s^2-9s+2}{2}$. (53)

And the relation between r and q is $r = q + 2q^2$. (54)

Fig. 11

Fig. 12

The graphical representation of r with respect to s is shown in Fig. 11, and Fig. 12 is the graphical representation of r with respect to q . In the r - s graph initial graph indicates the Chaplygin gas model ($r > 1, s < 0$) then graph shows Λ CDM model ($r = 1, s = 0$).

8. Discussion of Observational Constraints

In this section, we consider the measurement of cosmological distances at a significant redshift. Such measurements help us to find out the expansion history of the universe and to determine whether the expansion is accelerating or decelerating, along with the associated rate.

Look-back time

The look-back time $t_L(z)$ is defined as the elapsed time between the present age of the universe t_0 and the time t when the light from a cosmic source at a particular redshift z was emitted. The Look-back time t_L (Krisciunas, 1993) is defined as $t_L(z) = t_0 - t(z) = \int_R^{R_0} \frac{dR}{R}$ where R_0 is the present value of the scale factor and $1 + z = \frac{R_0}{R}$ also t_0 is the current age of the universe and z is the redshift of the measured amount of light from the galaxy.

The Look-back time in the redshift for the studied model is obtained as

$$t_L(z) = \frac{1}{nB} \left[1 - \frac{1}{(1+z)^n} \right] \quad (55)$$

Proper distance $d_p(z)$

The proper distance $d_p(z)$ is defined as the distance between a cosmic source emitting light at any instant $t = t_1$ located at $r = r_1$ with redshift z an observer at $r = 0$ and $t = t_0$ receiving the light from the source emitted, that is $d_p(z) = r_1 R_0$ where $r_1 = \int_0^z \frac{dz'}{H(z')}$.

Hence, the proper distance $d_p(z)$ (Hogg, 1999) is defined as $d_p(z) = R_0 \int_0^z \frac{dz'}{H(z')}$

For the studied model, the proper distance is obtained as

$$d_p(z) = \frac{1}{B(1-n)} [(1+z)^{1-n} - 1], \quad \text{for } n \neq 1. \quad (56)$$

Fig. 13

Fig.13 indicates the graphical representation of the proper distance with respect to redshift z .

Luminosity distance $d_L(z)$

The luminosity distance $d_L(z)$ is a fundamental concept in observational cosmology which connects an object's intrinsic luminosity to its observed flux. In an expanding universe, for a light source at redshift z , the luminosity distance is related to the proper distance. The relation between Luminosity distance and Proper distance is

$$d_L(z) = (1+z)d_p(z)$$

$$d_L(z) = \frac{(1+z)[(1+z)^{1-n}-1]}{B(1-n)}, \quad \text{for } n \neq 1. \quad (57)$$

Fig.14

Fig.14 indicates the graphical representation of luminosity distance with respect to redshift z .

Angular diameter distance $d_A(z)$

The angular diameter distance is a cosmological distance measure that relates the physical size of an object to its angular size it appears to have on the sky. The angular diameter distance is defined as $d_A(z) = \frac{d_L(z)}{(1+z)^2}$ (Demianski, et al., 2003).

The angular diameter distance is obtained as

$$d_L(z) = \frac{[(1+z)^{1-n}-1]}{B(1-n)(1+z)}, \quad \text{for } n \neq 1. \quad (58)$$

Fig. 15

Fig.15 indicates the graphical representation of the angular diameter distance with respect to redshift z .

Jerk parameter j

Jerk parameter measures the rate of change of the acceleration of the universe and is defined as a dimensionless third derivative of the scale factor with respect to cosmic time t (Visser, 2004).

$$j = \frac{1}{H^3 R} \frac{d^3 R(t)}{dt^3}$$

$$j = (1-n)(1-2n). \quad (59)$$

Cosmic snap parameter s

The cosmic snap parameter in cosmology is a dimensionless parameter, and it is useful in describing deviations from Λ CDM or kinematic cosmology. The snap parameter is defined as the dimensionless fourth derivative of the scale factor with respect to cosmic time t (Visser, 2004).

$$s = \frac{1}{H^4 R} \frac{d^4 R(t)}{dt^4}$$

$$s = (1 - n)(1 - 2n)(1 - 3n). \quad (60)$$

9. Conclusion

In this paper, we have described the stability of a plane symmetric cosmological model filled with wet dark fluid (WDF), which is one of the forms of dark energy in $f(R, T)$ theory of gravitation. The solutions of the field equation are obtained by considering the relation between the Hubble parameter and scale factor, i.e. Hubble law.

The mean Hubble parameter decreases to zero as time $t \rightarrow \infty$ and increases as redshift $z \rightarrow \infty$ (as shown in Fig. 1). The expansion scalar, shear scalar, and anisotropic expansion parameter gradually decrease to zero as time t increases and increases as redshift $z \rightarrow \infty$ (as shown in fig. 2-4). Hence, we can say that the universe is expanding at a small rate of expansion, and also the universe starts with an anisotropic state, but can approach isotropy. The deceleration parameter of the model depends on the value of n , if $n > 1$, the value of the deceleration parameter is positive, which indicates that the universe is decelerating, and the universe is accelerating for the range $0 < n < 1$. The wet dark fluid pressure $p_{WDF} \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$, i. e. pressureless dark energy (Chan, 2015). The wet dark fluid density ρ_{WDF} decreases with time t increases, which concludes the expansion of the universe. Also p_{WDF} and ρ_{WDF} increases as the redshift z increases (as shown in Fig.5-8), which indicates the early universe was higher in temperature and smaller in size. The above observations are in good agreement with the current observations. The derived model is stable within the range $0 < \gamma < 1$. The WEC, NEC, DEC, and SEC are satisfied, which indicates the WDF model depicts a stable, non-exotic cosmological fluid. The statefinder parameter pair $\{r, s\} \rightarrow \{1, 0\}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ hence our model approaches to Λ CDM model for a large value of n . In the r - s graph (Fig. 11), the initial graph indicates the Chaplygin gas model ($r > 1, s < 0$) and then the graph indicates the Λ CDM model ($r = 1, s = 0$). The proper distance increases with redshift (Fig. 13) and attains a constant value with an increase in redshift. The luminosity distance increases linearly with redshift $z \rightarrow \infty$ (Fig. 14). The angular diameter distance initially increases as redshift increases, but then it decreases gradually and attains some constant value as redshift $z \rightarrow \infty$. The solutions of observational parameters such as look-back time, proper distance, angular diameter, and snap parameter are in good agreement with the current observations. For the appropriate choice of the value of n , the jerk parameter j gives a positive value which indicates there is a transition of the universe from a decelerating to an accelerating phase.

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